

Research

Seismic Performance of Steel-Confined High-Performance Concrete Shear Wall

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Abstract: Natural disasters, such as earthquakes, often lead to the destruction or even collapse of buildings. The selection of a suitable earthquake-resistant structure is crucial and may include steel structures, reinforced concrete structures, high-performance concrete structures and other composite structures with high strength and toughness, etc. Using the advantages of steel construction and high-performance concrete wall panel construction to form a combined system of earthquake-resistant steel frame structures and finished concrete wall panels can effectively improve the seismic characteristics of the structure.

This article proposes a study of a steel frame structure bounded by concrete wall panels, and its seismic characteristics as well as a creation of an improved models of finite element analysis of eight structures under horizontal low cyclic reciprocating loads. And the findings are summarised as follow:

1. The calculation of eight walls is compared with each other, taking into account the influence of the geometry of the structure, material, contact nonlinearity, etc. Based on the proven finite element model, the influence of concrete aggregates on the seismic characteristics of the entire structure.
2. Results show that, although highly efficient concrete-filled wall panels reduce the plasticity of the structure to a certain extent, they can effectively increase the load-bearing capacity and overall energy consumption of the entire structure
3. In the absence of a steel frame, the maximum bearing capacity of the four wall panels is comparable, and the properties of CC and RAC have minimal impact on the ultimate bearing capacity and plasticity of the panels.

In the presence of a steel frame, the sample with UHPC as the frame of the wall panel exhibits significantly increased bearing capacity and enhanced energy dissipation capacity.

Keywords: Composite panels, Steel frames, Hysteretic behavior, Low cyclic loading tests

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Introduction

In frame constructions, infilled walls often function as interior dividers or outside claddings. As a result, the general behaviour of the building is never taken into consideration while designing the structures. However, it is well known that the presence of infills inside of buildings significantly improves their lateral stiffness, ultimate strength and energy dissipation capacity against earthquakes, even though infilled walls are generally regarded as non-structural parts. Numerous studies have been conducted to analyse and develop infilled frames that have traditional walls constructed of concrete or bricks when subjected to in-plane forces.

Sixty five substantial infilled steel frames were subjected to parameter investigation by Polyakov, where masonry units, mortar, the loading mechanism, and wall apertures were among the characteristics [1, 2]. A three-story, three-bay frame of one-quarter scale was also explored in addition to individual panels. Polyakov came to the conclusion that the multi-story, multi-bay infilled frame acted as a collection of separately braced frames rather than a monolith. Papia et al. and Cavaleri et al. identified a diagonal pin-jointed strut as being able to reproduce the horizontal force-inter-storey displacement cycle law of the real masonry infill, which further supported the braced frame concept. In contrast to earlier empirical techniques, the suggested method emphasises the axial stiffness of the frame's columns rather than their flexural stiffness. An experimental examination using one story, single bay infilled reinforced concrete was conducted to complement the analytical debate. The suggested model was enhanced by taking into consideration the experimental findings[3, 4].

For estimating the ultimate load and lateral displacement of steel frames with brickwork or concrete infilling, Holmes offered a straightforward method, by assuming that the interaction between the steel frame and infilling varies linearly along the frame beam, the wall panel was replaced by an equivalent strut in the analytical model, whose cross sectional area was calculated as $td/3$, the results of thirteen tests are then compared[5]. Further research was done on the streamlined equivalent strut for concrete block masonry walls[6]. Quarter-scale semi-rigidly linked steel frames served as the examples, which were filled with non-integral, unreinforced concrete block masonry walls. The investigation focused on four main factors: the number of bays, the composition of the concrete blocks the mortar joint and the kind of infill apertures. Additionally, a model for the hysteresis loop was developed along with a proposed model for similar struts with varying cross-sectional areas.

The non-linear behaviour of a pair of four-storey single-span infilled frames was investigated theoretically and experimentally by other researchers [7, 8]. Since the infill and the frame are bonded or connected together in integral infilled frames, the effects of the connectors on the stiffness and strength of the infilled frames were examined. This demonstrated that the strength of non-integral infilled frames was dependent on the bending strength of the frame.

Moghadam et al. and Mohammadi et al. conducted an intensive research on the seismic behaviour of infilled frames and the research results included many aspects, such as the crack strength determination of infilled steel frames, the impact of repair and retrofit on in-plane behaviour of masonry infilled steel frames, seismic strengthening of masonry infilled structures, mathematical functions to evaluate stress of infilled frames, discrete element method in the nonlinear analysis of masonry-infilled steel frames with opening[9-13].

The seismic behaviour of headed shear stud connectors used in steel frames with partly restrained connections and reinforced concrete infill walls was described by Saari et al., a number of design equations were confirmed, and an experimental programme was created to assess the strength and deformation capacity of shear studs for use in S-RCW infill systems[14]. Tong et al.'s examination of the experimental and cyclic behaviour of a composite structural system made up of partially-restrained steel frames with reinforced concrete infill walls was inspired by the work on headed stud connections[15]. According to the studies, the technology might potentially provide low to moderate rise buildings in earthquake-prone areas with strength sufficient to withstand seismic forces and stiffness sufficient to limit drift.

Liu Yushu et al. through the 7-layer single-span two-story steel frame structure with and without walls, perform low-cycle reciprocating loading tests and horizontal static testing. The test revealed that the filled wall can increase the structure's overall stiffness and bearing capacity. According to the analysis of the test parameters, the limit value of the seismic elastic inter-layer displacement angle of the flexible steel frame structure with lightweight filled wall is proposed. The hysteresis curve of the pure frame is plump and fusiform, demonstrating good energy consumption capacity, while the hysteresis curve with the filled wall is closer to the anti-S shape, demonstrating the effect of slippage after the wall cracks[16].

Hou Hetao et al., studied the hysteresis performance of 8-layer single-span steel frame with energy-saving composite wall panels. According to tests, the embedded pieces that are connected to the steel frame and the energy-efficient composite wall panel are where most of the damage is focused, reliable connection elements are a crucial need to make sure the wall and main structure function together, the seismic performance of the structure can be enhanced by increasing the thickness of the wall panel[17].

Cao Zhenggang et al., studied the effects of ALC (i.e., Autoclaved Lightweight Concrete) filling wall and LSF (i.e., Lightweight steel frame) dry filling wall on the seismic performance of assembled steel frames with variable beam and high beam column nodes. It was found that the assembled steel frame of the variable beam high beam column node itself has good carrying capacity, anti-side stiffness and ductility, and the initial stiffness, peak load and energy consumption capacity of the steel frame filled with ALC filling wall are significantly improved relative to the empty frame. The ALC wall can delay the failure of the steel frame, but the LSF dry filling wall can ignore its impact on the steel frame due to its small bending stiffness in the plane[18].

Wang et al., studied the influence of ALC filling wall on the seismic performance of CFST frame (i.e., Concrete-filled steel tubular) and its damage model. The findings demonstrated that the wall panel's components embedded in the CFST frame were particularly vulnerable to damage, as were the connecting portions between the wall panel and the latter. The ALC block wall developed several 45° oblique fractures, and some of the connecting elements were either loose or broken. Despite these issues, the construction had high hysteresis performance and ductility. The strength and stiffness of the CFST frame with integrated ALC wall panels or ALC masonry have greatly outperformed the strength and stiffness of the pure CFST frame when compared to the CFST frame with external ALC wall panels[19].

In order to study the influence of the surrounding wall on the lateral force resistance of the steel frame, a quasi-static test of the ALC wall panel embedded in the steel frame and the finite element analysis of the corresponding model were carried out. The findings demonstrate that as the load increases, the diagonal jacking phenomenon of the ALC wall panel becomes evident; this phenomenon is comparable to the effect of oblique support rods; cracks are concentrated near the nodes of the wall panel; and the ALC wall panel can effectively prevent the rapid deterioration of the stiffness of the steel frame in the early stage of force, as well as provide multiple seismic defences for the building[20].

Finite Element Analysis Of Seismic Behavior of a Frame Wall Structure

Introduction to the software

Comparatively speaking, ABAQUS software is quick, simple to use, and offers excellent human-computer interface features compared to other large-scale general-purpose finite element software. The programme is generally broken down into three sections: the pre-processing module, the analysis module, and the post-processing module. The model's constituent elements, interactions, and boundary conditions have been established. The post-processing module is in charge of examining, modifying, and showing the most recent findings of the model while the analysis module is in charge of iteratively computing the model using the finite element method. The ABAQUS programme includes robust

material models and strong nonlinear solution capabilities. The rule of stress development in a structure under load circumstances may be more precisely reflected by this method, which is well-known and frequently utilised in the field of civil engineering. This paper's simulation was run in ABAQUS CAE 2017. The unit size must be synchronised individually, because Abaqus lacks an easy unit setting. The scale for each physical quantity in this simulation is indicated in Table 1 in line with the unifying rules of the Abaqus unit comparison table.

Table 1. Corresponding program for each physical quantity

Length/warp	Stress/Modulus of Elasticity	force/load	density
Mm	MPa	N	t/mm3

Material structure

Steel

The research of the perfect elastoplastic model, double elastoplastic model, toughened elastoplastic model, etc., is currently close to being finished. Each defining model places emphasis on particular steel properties. The post-hardening model, which primarily considers the impact of steel hardening, is used in this article's two-fold elastoplastic linear steel hardening model. The model's schematic diagram is seen in Figure 1. Steel bar's modulus of elasticity, yield strength, and tensile strength were determined using material performance testing with a Poisson's ratio of 0.3.

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of two-wire steel model and armature

Concrete

Concrete's fundamental connections are rather intricate. The three concrete definition models created by ABAQUS are brittle cracking, diffusion cracking, and ductile damage. The plastic damage model is one of them and may be used to calculate mechanical characteristics numerically. It is frequently utilised in finite element modelling of concrete structures under cyclic loads. Consequently, the concrete deterioration caused by plastic is modelled in this study. The link between stress and strain when the material is under uniaxial tension and uniaxial compression, as well as the relationship between inelastic deformation and tensile and compressive damage factors, should be defined in the concrete plastic damage model.

According to the "Design Rules for Concrete Structures" (GB50010-2010, 2010), equation (1) is used for calculating uniaxial compressive stresses and deformations of concrete:

$$x = \frac{\epsilon}{\epsilon_c}$$

$$x = \frac{\varepsilon}{\varepsilon_c}$$

$$y = \begin{cases} \frac{nx}{n-1+x^n}, & x \leq 1 \\ \frac{x}{\alpha_c(x-1)^2+x}, & x \geq 1 \end{cases} \tag{1}$$

Where ε_c and α_c are the peak compressive stress and compressive stress-strain curve parameters, respectively, and the data interpolation method in the specification appendix table is used for calculation; f_c is the test value of the axial compressive strength of concrete and phosphogypsum, which are 33.06 MPa and 6.2 MPa, respectively. The calculated stress-strain curve of concrete is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Stress-strain curve of concrete under pressure

A formal criteria for a concrete plastic damage model is still lacking. The Birtel approach and the Sidirof energy equivalence concept are two calibration techniques that are often employed[21, 22]. Among these, the calculating technique founded on the Sidirof principle of energy equivalence is extensively applied, and the theoretical research is comparatively finished. It is appropriate for concrete deterioration from cyclic loads. The concrete plastic damage factor is determined using this approach. For the calculation formula, see equation (2).

$$\sigma = E_0(1 - d)^2\varepsilon \tag{2}$$

The above equation (2) for calculating the damage ratio is entered into the concrete compressive stress-strain, and equation (3) is used for calculating the compressive damage ratio.

$$d_t = \begin{cases} 1 - \sqrt{\frac{\rho_c n}{n-1+x^n}}, & x \leq 1 \\ 1 - \sqrt{\frac{\rho_c}{\alpha_c(x-1)^2+x}}, & x > 1 \end{cases}$$

(3)

$$\rho_c = \frac{f_c}{E_c \varepsilon_c}$$

According to the "Design Rules for Concrete Structures" (GB50010-2010, 2010), the equation (4) is used for calculating the stress-strain dependence of concrete in uniaxial tension is as follows:

$$x = \frac{\varepsilon}{\varepsilon_t}$$

$$y = \frac{\sigma}{f_t} \tag{4}$$

$$y = \begin{cases} 1.2x - 0.2x^6, & x \leq 1 \\ \frac{x}{\alpha_t(x-1)^{1.7} + x}, & x > 1 \end{cases}$$

Where ϵ_t and α_t are the parameters of the descending section of the peak tensile stress and tensile strain versus strain curve, respectively, calculated in accordance with the data interpolation method in the specification appendix table, and f_t is the tensile strength value of concrete. In this test, the splitting tensile strength of the material was 1.95 MPa and 0.39 MPa, respectively. Based on this, the stress-strain curve of concrete can be calculated as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Stress-strain curve for concrete

The above damage ratio calculation formula (2) is input into the concrete tensile stress-strain ratio formula (4) to obtain the tensile damage ratio calculation formula in formula (5).

$$d_t = \begin{cases} 1 - \sqrt{\rho_t(1.2 - 0.2x^5)}, & x \leq 1 \\ 1 - \sqrt{\frac{\rho_t}{\alpha_t(x-1)^{1.7} + x}}, & x > 1 \end{cases} \tag{5}$$

$$\rho_t = \frac{f_t}{E_c \epsilon_t}$$

Expanded polystyrene board (XPS)

The strength and rigidity of XPS board are low, the material is brittle, and this has little effect on the mechanical properties of the structure, and only plays the role of filling the gap. In order to meet model convergence requirements, the numerical analysis of the model reduces the XPS foam to an ideal elastic material. Reference materials for determining the performance parameters of materials are given in Table 2.

Table 2. XPS Board Basic Operating Parameters

Material	Density (t/mm ³)	Elastic modulus (MPa)	Poisson's ratio
XPS	2.8E-11	10	0.3

Sample design

Wireframe model

Structural frame material: ECC or UHPC; fill material: RAC (i.e., recycled fill concrete) or CC (i.e., conventional concrete).
 Frame 1: ECC structural frame, the middle wall is filled with CC, and the middle wall has no steel frame;

- Frame 2: ECC structural frame, the middle wall is filled with RAC, and the middle wall has no steel frame ;
- Frame 3: UHPC structural frame, the middle wall is filled with CC, and the middle wall has no steel frame ;
- Frame 4: UHPC structural frame, the middle wall is filled with RAC, and the middle wall has no steel frame. ;
- Frame 5: ECC structural frame, the middle wall is filled with CC, and the middle wall is steel framed. ;
- Frame 6: ECC structural frame, the middle wall is filled with RAC, and the middle wall is steel framed. ;
- Frame 7: UHPC structural frame, the middle wall is filled with CC, and the middle wall is steel framed. ;
- Frame 8: UHPC structural frame, middle wall filled with RAC and middle wall steel framed.

Steel frame structure

To ensure comparability, the dimensions, structural shapes, materials and manufacturing methods of the steel frames in this experiment are exactly the same. As shown in Figure 4, the steel is Q235B steel, the main span of the steel frame is 3000mm, the column height is 2950mm, the column is a square steel pipe column, the actual section size is 200×200×10mm, and the beam I-beam, actual section size HM240×175×7×11mm. The connection of the steel frame to the beam and column uses the outer ring plate connection, its detailed structure and dimensions are shown in Figure 5. The length of the overhanging end plate is 200 mm.

The length of the protrusion of the outer annular plate at the point is 60 mm. The flange of the steel beam and the end plate of the outrigger of the unit are butt welded with full penetration. The wall is spliced with two rows of bolts. bolts are made of high-strength M16 bolts of class 10.9. The study showed that the protruding parts of the outer ring plates on the east and west sides of the frame have little effect on the joint performance, and the stress and deformation are small. under the action of a horizontal load The outer annular plates of the nodes are lowered on both sides, and the lower beam is made according to the normal design.

Figure 4. Schematic Diagram of Steel Frame (SF)

Beam-column connection, front view

Beam-column connection, top view

(a) Connecting the top beam to the column

Front view of beam-to-column connection

Top view of beam-to-column connection

(b) Connecting the lower beam to the column

Figure 5. Structural diagram of beam-to-column connection

Structure of the fabricated composite wall panel

Precast composite wall panels consist of a reinforced concrete mesh frame and a composite binder based on CC or RAC as a filler. As shown in Figure 6, the wall size is 2760×1980mm. The thickness is 100 mm, the width of the "beams and columns" of the reinforced concrete lattice frame is 120 mm, the concrete of which consists of Ultra-High Performance Concrete (UHPC) or Engineered Cementitious Composite (ECC), steel rods of HRB400. The thickness of the concrete cover is taken as 15 mm, in accordance with the requirements of the "Reinforced Concrete Structures Design Rules" (GB50010-2010, 2010) for the minimum reinforcement coefficient of beams and columns and the "Uniform Specifications for the Use of Building Materials" (DBJ52T093-2019), 2019) for requirements for the reinforcement of reinforced concrete structural columns and horizontal anchor beams, the concrete "frame column" reinforcement is 4C12, the "frame beam" reinforcement is 4C8, and the "beam column" stirrup is C6@. 195. The detailed construction is as follows. As shown in Figure 7, the beam-column concrete reinforcement cross section is shown in Figure 8.

(a) The overall plan of the structure

(b) Longitudinal section view of the structure

(c) Structural cross-sectional view

Structure of ECC-CC

(a) The overall plan of the structure

(b) Longitudinal section view of the structure

(c) Structural cross-sectional view

Structure of ECC-RAC

(a) The overall plan of the structure

(b) Longitudinal section view of the structure

(c) Structural cross-sectional view

Structure of UHPC-CC

Structure of UHPC-RAC

Figure 6. General layout of the composite wall structure

Figure 7. Concrete frame reinforcement scheme

Figure 8. Scheme of reinforcement of the concrete section "beam-column"

The aggregate size is 760×500mm, and the infill rate of the composite wallboard in this paper is 59.3%. To prevent the composite aggregate from falling out under the action of transport, installation and seismic loads, the composite aggregate is designed to be connected to concrete in the form of a gap, and its specific structure is shown in Fig. 9.

Figure 9. Composition of phosphogypsum and concrete

Calculation of the scheme of connection of a steel frame with a composite wall

A reasonable and reliable connection method between the steel frame and the composite wall is a prerequisite for structural safety and good interoperability. The wall must be secure with surrounding steel members. It is connected and can accommodate the inter-floor displacements of the main structure in different directions, as shown in the general plan and cross section of the structure in Figure 10, a flexible connection pattern is used between the steel frame and the composite wall to prevent horizontal seismic loads from affecting the main part of the steel frames. There is direct rigid contact between the structure and the composite wall. A 20mm release joint is installed between the composite wall, steel frame column and top beam. The separation joint is sealed with Styrofoam board with good compression. The detailed structure is shown in Figure 2-10. The out-of-plane constraint of the composite wall panel uses L-clamps, and a total of 16 L-clamps front and rear are distributed in beam-column nodes in the middle of the concrete trellis frame.

Structure of SF-ECC-CC

(a) The overall plan of the structure

(b) Longitudinal section view of the structure

(c) Structural cross-sectional view

Structure of SF-ECC-RAC

(a) The overall plan of the structure

(b) Longitudinal section view of the structure

(c) Structural cross-sectional view

Structure of SF-UHPC-RAC

Structure of SF-UHPC-CC

Figure 10. General Plan and Cross Section of Concrete Steel Frame Composite Wall Panel

Setting options associated with the end element

Interaction

The mutual use of different parts of the model in ABAQUS must be explained according to the actual situation in the model. The actual connection between steels in this model is welding, and the finite element model is simplified to bonding contact. In the real model, each fill material is filled between the steel frame and the concrete frame. In order to ensure its stability under cyclic loading, as well as to meet the convergence requirements in the model, the filler has bonding contact with the steel frame, and the concrete lattice frame has surface contact, and the coefficient of friction is set to 0.3. The packing and framework of the concrete lattice will slide relatively each other under the action of a circulating load, so the contact method is set to surface-to-surface contact. Referring to the provisions of "Specification for Masonry Structure" (GB 50003-2011, 2011), the coefficient of dry friction between aggregate and concrete is set to 0.7, and the coefficient of friction between the bottom beam of the concrete frame and steel is set to 0.45. This model accepts built-in constraints, independent of reinforced concrete slip. In order to simulate the actual situation of applying a load to the two ends of the steel frame column by connecting the loading plate to the surrounding steel bar under the actual load, the interaction between the loading plate and the end of the steel frame column in this model is set to surface to surface contact, with a coefficient of friction of 0.2, the left and right load plates are connected to the control point RP3, and a cyclic load is applied to the control point RP3 to ensure that the direction of the load and the displacement of the two load plates are the same, regardless of the influence of the deformation of the guardrail steel bar. In addition, the model simplifies the installation of the carrier plate on a solid body without taking into account its deformation effect. The loading diagram is shown in Figure 11.

Figure 11. Schematic diagram of model interaction

Boundary conditions and loads

The boundary conditions and the loading scheme must also be set according to the actual situation. During the test, a SF (i.e., steel frame) wall panel model is used, the base of the steel frame column is bolted to the base, and the displacement meter does not detect significant displacement; for the wall panel model without SF, the bottom of the wall panel is fully hinged and the reference point is fixed at the centre of the top surface of the wall. It is used to load horizontal masses with a low reciprocating cycle and limit their displacement and rotation in the y and z axes. The model idealizes the lower column as a consolidation, and to simplify the calculation, the model is simplified to out-of-plane constraints (Y direction); to ensure the best convergence of the model, the model uses a bias load throughout the process. Before the local movement of the rod (corresponding to the test), the displacement loading system is 5 mm, and the subsequent loading system is exactly the same as the test loading system. The specific circuit diagram is shown in Figure 12.

Figure 12. The fundamental diagram of the boundary conditions and loads

Selecting a grid of units

Considering the calculation accuracy and the calculation efficiency of the model, all parts of the steel structures of this model are modelled using shell blocks, and the block type is S4R; concrete framing, phosphogypsum and foam panels are modelled using solid blocks and the block type is C3D8R; steel bars are modelled using 3D truss frame blocks and the block type is T3D2. The mesh size has a great influence on the convergence, calculation accuracy, and efficiency of the model calculation. A finer grid size can provide convergence to a certain extent and improve the accuracy of the calculation, but this will significantly reduce the efficiency of the calculation. In addition, the components in this model

have the characteristics of multiple components, multiple materials, complex contacts, etc., and the calculation efficiency is low. Therefore, after many trial calculations, the model determined that in the parts where the structural stress is more concentrated or the deformation is larger, the mesh size is set smaller, the minimum size is 30mm, and the mesh size of other components is correspondingly increased, the maximum size is 70mm. The division of the grid of cells is shown in Figure 13.

Figure 13. Model cell grid

Analysis of Finite Element Results

Mises stress contour analysis

(1) Analysis of the Mises stress cloud map for reinforcement

Figure 14 shows a diagram of the Mises stress cloud for reinforcement at the peak point of the frame curve of 8 models. As can be seen from the figure, under the action of reciprocating load, the stress of the beam reinforcement of eight model structures is higher than that of the vertical column, which indicates that the stress is mainly concentrated on the beam, implementing the reasonable design principle of “strong column and weak beam”. When the peak point of the frame curve is reached, the stress in the steel rods of most wall structures with RAC as the filling element is higher than in wall structures with CC as the filling element, and the high stress is mainly concentrated in the two middle beams. Compared to the model without a steel frame structure, the stress of the model with a SF structure “increases”. The stress is concentrated not only in the middle of the two transverse steel rods, but also on the steel rods of the beam on both edges. The phenomenon of high voltage also occurs. This shows that with an increase in the strength of the steel frame filled with a steel frame structure, the force of the steel rod will be changed. This is due to the fact that when the wall is subjected to horizontal load, the steel frame structure can provide greater resistance to the transfer of lateral force to the steel rod. Consequently, even more steel bars are amenable.

Figure 14. Diagram of the Mises reinforcement stress cloud for 8 models

(2) Analysis of the stress cloud map by Mises of the wall panel frame

Figure 15 shows a diagram of the stress cloud according to the Mises of the frame of wall panels of 8 models at the peak point of the curve of the frame. As can be seen from the figure, at the peak point of the frame curve, the stress in the concrete connecting groove between the beam and the vertical column in a non-steel frame is higher, which indicates that when exposed to a horizontal load, it is likely to collapse first. Compared with SF, when the construction of a wall panel without a steel frame reaches the yield point, the stress concentration point decreases mainly at the junction of the edge beam and the vertical column, as well as in the upper left and right corners. This shows that the steel frame can reduce the damage to the concrete memory card slot. This is because the filled RAC and the concrete memory card slot work together to resist external influences, thereby reducing damage to the concrete memory card slot.

Figure 15. Diagrams of Mises stress clouds for eight models of wall panel frames

(3) Mises stress analysis in the filler

Figure 16 shows a diagram of the Mises stress cloud for the filler of 8 models at the peak point of the frame curve. As can be seen from the figure, when at the peak point of the frame curve, the maximum stress of each beam and vertical column of a wall structure with a steel frame is significantly greater than that of a wall structure without a steel frame, and a wider area of plastic deformation appears. Deformation. This is due to the fact that under the action of a reciprocating load, concrete is damaged due to reciprocating tensile and compressive stresses and sliding between the steel rod and concrete. As the load displacement increases, the damage accumulates and the damage area increases.

When the UHPC-RAC reaches the yield point, the stress is also mainly concentrated at the four corners or at the junction of the beam and the vertical column. Compared to ECC-RAC, the UHPC-RAC voltage has increased when the yield strength is reached, but the force situation is similar. When the beam reaches the yield point, the UHPC-RAC voltage increases. the point of application of force remains unchanged, more concrete columns are exposed to force. When the filling element is replaced with CC, it can be clearly detected that the stress concentration point of UHPC-CC is less than that of UHPC-RAC, and the voltage is less.

Figure 16. Mises stress cloud diagram for 8 filler models

(4) Mises stress analysis in the SF steel frame

Figure 17 shows the diagram of the stress cloud by the Mises of the steel frame at the peak point of the curve of the frame of four wall panels with models of the SF structure. As can be seen from the figure, at the peak point of the frame curve, the stress distribution of SF-ECC-CC is more concentrated than that of the other three models, which is mainly reflected in the direction of the upper beam, while the stress of the other three models is more scattered, mainly focused on the connection of the upper beam and the position of the lower support column. In addition, the maximum voltage of the four models is not much different. This is due to the fact that when exposed to horizontal force, the filling body

is destroyed first than the reinforced concrete frame, which reduces interaction with the reinforced concrete frame and reduces the force, therefore there are fewer stress points at the junction of the elements. beam and vertical column. This shows that with a certain strength of steel rods and concrete, a steel frame can reduce damage to the card slot made of concrete. This is because the filling housing and the concrete card slot work together to resist external forces, thereby reducing damage to the concrete card slot.

Figure 17. Diagram of the stress cloud according to the Mises of the steel frame of the SF model

Analysis of the equivalent plastic deformation cloud map

(1) Analysis of an equivalent cloud map of plastic deformations of steel rods

Figure 18 shows an equivalent diagram of a cloud of plastic deformations of steel rods of 8 models at the peak point of the frame curve. As can be seen from the figure, under the action of reciprocating load, the deformation of models of four wall panels with steel frames is less than that of structures of four wall panels without steel frames, which shows that the steel frame protects the internal reinforced concrete frame structure to a certain extent; among the four structures without steel frames, ECC-CC has the least deformation compared to the other three wall structures. At the same time, ECC-CC has the least deformation compared to ECC-RAC, and UHPC-CC has the least deformation compared to UHPC-RAC, which indicates that CC is somewhat smaller in size than as a filling element, RAC can better reduce the load on the reinforced concrete frame.

Figure 18. Equivalent diagram of a cloud of plastic deformations of 8 models of steel rods

(2) Analysis of the equivalent cloud map of plastic deformations of the wall panel frame

Figure 19 shows the contours of the equivalent plastic deformation of the wall panel frame at the peak point of the frame curve for eight models. It can be seen from the figure that under the action of reciprocating loading, when the frame of the wall panel is under compression, the stresses on the two middle columns are greatest, and the stresses on the side columns on both sides are relatively small, regardless of whether the grid is filled or not. The primary places are the intersecting joints between the middle column of the frame and the ceiling beam and the inter-story beam, as well as the inner side of the connection of the side column with the ceiling beam, where stresses and a large force are

concentrated. where cracks appear. In a real test, cracks can be detected primarily from this location. The stress in the middle of the floor beam is relatively greater than in other places, which is consistent with a large bending moment in the middle of the span of conventional beams under uniform load. However, due to the presence of a central column, the bending moment in the middle part of the floor beam is reduced, and the overall bearing capacity of the wall is improved.

Figure 19. Diagrams of the cloud of equivalent plastic deformations of eight types of frames of wall panel models
 (3) Image analysis of a cloud equivalent to plastic deformation of the filler body

Figure 20 shows the contours of the equivalent plastic deformation of the filler at the peak point of the skeletal curve for eight models. It can be seen from the figure that under the action of reciprocating load, the stress cloud diagram of the wall panel model with a steel frame and the wall panel model without a steel frame shows that when the wall reaches its maximum bearing capacity, the pressure of the wall model without a steel frame is mainly concentrated on the surrounding filler housing, the middle filler housing carries less force, and the four corners the filler walls also carry more pressure, so that more stress is concentrated in a relatively weak area around the wall, which does not contribute to the power of improving the performance of the wall. On the other hand, the pressure of the steel-framed wall model is mainly concentrated on the middle part of the filler body, especially the middle part of the filler body withstands the highest pressure, so that the stress cloud diagram on the filler body is distributed more evenly, and the filling body and the frame form a joint tension. In general, it carries and transmits the upper load, improves the mechanical characteristics of the wall, reduces the likelihood of loss of structural load-bearing capacity due to the failure of only the central column.

(a) Specimen ECC-CC

(b) Specimen ECC-RAC

(c) Specimen UHPC-CC

(d) Specimen UHPC-RAC

(e) Specimen SF-ECC-CC

(f) Specimen SF-ECC-RAC

Figure 20. Cloud diagrams of equivalent plastic deformations 8 types of filler models

(4) Analysis of the contour of equivalent plastic deformation of the frame made of structural steel SF

Figure 21 shows diagrams of a cloud of equivalent plastic deformations of a steel frame at the peak point of the frame curve for four SF structural wall models. It can be seen from the figure that during reciprocating loading, it is possible to compare and analyse the stress contours of steel frames at the peak point of the skeletal curve of the four models of SF load-bearing walls, as well as the distribution of forces of the lateral columns of the frame. The ECC wall panel frame is better than that of the UHPC frame side. Columns, concrete side columns and internal fittings better distribute the pressure transmitted from the top of the steel frame beam. From the stress diagram of the steel frame, it can be seen that the stress of the ECC wall panel frame in the steel frame is also more uniform than the stress of the UHPC wall panel frame, which can better transmit and carry the upper load and improve the plasticity of the entire wall. Another improvement in physical characteristics. It is because of the presence of filler that the transmission carries the upper load and reduces the bearing capacity of the central rack. The joint force of the frame and filler is the main reason for the difference between the wall and the wall without filler, and the main reason for using filler is to reduce the difference in axial forces between the columns of the frame.

Figure 21. Diagram of the equivalent cloud of plastic deformations of the SF model steel frame

Analysis of the hysteresis curve

The curve of the load created by the structure when it is subjected to a low-cycle reciprocating horizontal load, which changes when moving, is called the hysteresis curve, which is often used to assess the seismic characteristics of the structure. The hysteresis curve mainly has the following four shapes: (1) fusiform: the curve is complete, and the component has excellent seismic and plastic deformation properties; (2) arc-shaped: the degree of completeness of the curve is worse than that of the fusiform, demonstrating a certain “pinching” effect, indicating that the component has slippage, but it still has excellent seismic properties and energy consumption; (3) Anti-S-shaped: the degree of completeness of the curve is low, more slippage is affected by seismic resistance and energy consumption the components are bad; (4) Z-shaped: the component is subject to more slippage, the curve is Z-shaped, and the component is seismic and consumes a lot of energy and low performance.

Figure 22 shows the hysteresis curves of 8 models. The figure shows that the residual deformation of the wall panel due to a low-cycle reciprocating horizontal load increases, accompanied by a decrease in the slope of the hysteresis curve. The hysteresis curve of the construction of wall panels with a steel frame is more complete than that of the construction of wall panels without a steel frame, which indicates that the construction of wall panels with a steel frame has the best characteristics of working together with concrete, can effectively carry the load, and the filling of the CC and RAC frame has negligible effects on the ultimate bearing capacity of the wall panel. Comparing the hysteresis curve of the wall panel structure with UHPC as the wall frame and the wall panel structure with ECC as the wall frame, it can be found that the shape of the hysteresis ring of each curve is similar, but the total area of the hysteresis ring of the wall panel structure with UHPC as the wall frame is greater, and the peak point is higher, indicating that that it collects more energy, indicating that UHPC as a wall frame will increase the strength of the wall panel. Using UHPC as a wall frame is more efficient than using ECC as a wall frame to increase the load-bearing capacity of wall panels. The hysteresis loop becomes more complete with increasing displacement, the energy consumption and peak load-bearing capacity of the structure increase, and the integrity of the structure improves.

(a) Specimen ECC-CC

(b) Specimen ECC-RAC

(c) Specimen UHPC-CC

(d) Specimen UHPC-RAC

(e) Specimen SF-ECC-CC

(f) Specimen SF-ECC-RAC

(g) Specimen SF-UHPC-CC

(h) Specimen SF-UHPC-RAC

Figure 22. Comparison of hysteresis curves of 8 models

Comparison of skeleton curves

The external network formed by the connection of the hysteresis curve with the peak load is called the frame curve. Through the frame curve, one can see the strength characteristics of the sample at different stages and various characteristic points of the elasticity curve. Figures 23 and 24 show the curves of the frame of 8 model wall structures. As can be seen from the figure, a longitudinal comparison shows that in the case of both steel frames and without steel frames, as well as under certain conditions of the wall panel frame, various fillers have a negligible effect on the final

bearing capacity of the wall panel. At the same time, comparing the wall panel designs of the four groups of models without steel frames, it was found that the maximum load-bearing capacity of the four groups of models with steel frames did not differ much, while the maximum load-bearing capacity of the four groups of models with steel frames was much higher than that of one of the four groups of models without steel frames, indicating that the wall structure with a steel frame has a good load-bearing capacity. Comparing the frame curve of the wall panel construction with UHPC as the wall frame and the wall panel construction with ECC as the wall frame, it can be found that the ultimate load-bearing capacity of the wall panel construction with UHPC as the wall frame and the wall panel construction with ECC as the wall frame has been significantly improved the wall panel construction with UHPC as the frame the wall that has the best bearing capacity. After the peak load at each bend, the bearing capacity decreases slightly until it decreases again. This is due to the fact that after the peak load, the frame of the wall panel collapses due to high stress concentration, and a plastic hinge forms at the end of the frame column, and the load-bearing capacity of the structure decreases, but the broken frame of the UHPC wall panel and the frame still have good synergetic properties, so the magnitude of the strength reduction is small when the concrete is damaged, peels off or lends itself to a large number of steel rods, the bearing capacity of the wall is significantly reduced. Through the analysis of the frame curve, it can be seen that the steel frame can provide better load-bearing capacity of the wall panel structure, and the construction of wall panels with UHPC as the wall frame can effectively increase the load-bearing capacity of the structure.

(a) Specimen ECC-CC

(b) Specimen ECC-RAC

(c) Specimen UHPC-CC

(d) Specimen UHPC-RAC

(e) Specimen SF-ECC-CC

(f) Specimen SF-ECC-RAC

(g) Specimen SF-UHPC-CC

(h) Specimen SF-UHPC-RAC

Figure 23. Skeletal curves of 8 models

(a) Model without steel frame

(b) Model with steel frame

Figure 24. Comparison of skeletal curves

Analysis of stiffness reduction

The stiffness reduction component refers to the phenomenon when the component is damaged and cracked due to reciprocating force, and the stiffness of the component decreases due to plastic development and accumulation of damage to the component with an increase in reciprocating force and displacement. In this paper, secant stiffness is used to evaluate the law of stiffness degradation (GB50011, 2010), following equation (6):

$$K_i = \frac{|+F_i|+|-F_j|}{|+x_i|+|-x_j|} \tag{6}$$

K_i- Secant stiffness under cyclic load of level I

F_i- i-th value of the load at the peak point

X_j- the value of the offset of the i-th peak point

Figure 25 shows the stiffness reduction curves of 8 model wall panel designs. As can be seen from the figure, the stiffness reduction curve of 8 groups of wall structures has basically gone through the following three stages: (1) At the early stage of load application, the stiffness of the sample decreases relatively quickly, (2) At the middle stage, as the displacement increases, the stiffness of the sample decreases, and (3) At the late stage, the stiffness deterioration has the tendency to level off as the load displacement increases. This is because with an increase in displacement, the steel rod gradually passes into the stage of plasticity. At the same time, the cracking of PGCM and the concrete frame leads to a decrease in its ability to withstand lateral loads, and energy is dissipated due to continuous opening and closing, friction and bite between fills cracks, so the rigidity of the structure is significantly reduced until it becomes soft. The initial stiffness of ECC-CC, ECC-RAC and UHPC-RAC is less than that of other wall structures, and the difference is small, indicating low lateral resistance of ECC-CC, ECC-RAC and UHPC-RAC. By increasing the steel frame, the lateral rigidity of the wall panel structure can be improved. In four groups of wall panel structures with steel frames, the stiffness reduction curve of the same wall frame structure is compared, and the stiffness of the filled RAC is higher than that of the filled CC, which indicates that the wall structure filled with RAC has a higher initial structural rigidity and destructive rigidity, but the fragility of the wall structure is also increases with increasing strength, so when the breaking capacity of the wall is reached, the wall collapses quickly, and the corresponding stiffness also decreases faster. In addition, in the case of the same filling material, comparing the effect of different frames of wall panels on the rigidity of the wall, it was found that the difference is small, indicating that different wall frames have a negligible effect on the initial rigidity and destructive rigidity of the wall structure.

(a) Specimen ECC-CC

(b) Specimen ECC-RAC

(c) Specimen UHPC-CC

(d) Specimen UHPC-RAC

(e) Specimen SF-ECC-CC

(f) Specimen SF-ECC-RAC

(g) Specimen SF-UHPC-CC

(h) Specimen SF-UHPC-RAC

Figure 25. Comparison of stiffness reduction curves of 8 models

Comparison of energy consumption capacity

(1) The value of energy consumption in one week

The area surrounded by one hysteresis loop represents the energy consumption per load cycle. Figure 26 shows the energy consumption of each load ring from 8 groups of model wall structures. It can be seen from the figure that in the elastic stage, as the displacement increases, the energy consumption of each group of wall panels gradually increases,

and when the displacement exceeds the yield strength, the sample is damaged, since the fillers inside the frame cannot interact with each other to resist the transverse force, the power consumption of energy decreases. However, the energy dissipation capacity of each group of wall structures increases linearly with increasing load displacement. After the displacement is greater than the yield displacement, the cycle of the hysteresis loop of each stage is 3 times, and the energy consumption of the second and third hysteresis loop is always less than the first hysteresis loop by 1 time, this is due to the accumulation of damage to the sample under reciprocating load, so the energy dissipation is weakened.

(a) Specimen ECC-CC

(b) Specimen ECC-RAC

(c) Specimen UHPC-CC

(d) Specimen UHPC-RAC

(e) Specimen SF-ECC-CC

(f) Specimen SF-ECC-RAC

(g) Specimen SF-UHPC-CC

(h) Specimen SF-UHPC-RAC

Figure 26 Comparison of power consumption curves of 8 models in one week

(2) The total value of energy consumption

The power consumption curve of the SF-CF component and the SF-PCW component is shown in Figure 27. As can be seen from the energy consumption curve, the energy consumption of the two components ECC-CC and ECC-RAC is basically the same throughout the loading stage, while the energy consumption of the other six groups of model wall structures with RAC as filler is significantly higher than that of the wall structure with CC as filler, since the steel frame, wall panels and the pure steel bars are basically the same at the initial loading stage. There is no direct contact with the concrete frame. Energy is mainly consumed by the steel frame structure. In the middle of the load, as the lateral displacement increases, the steel frame is in direct contact with the composite wall and reinforced concrete frame, filling the composite wall and frame as a structural system. In addition, as can be seen from Figure 28, in the absence of a steel frame, the energy consumption values of ECC-CC and ECC-RAC samples are almost the same; the energy consumption values of samples with UHPC as a wall panel frame are large, but the increase is not very large. In the presence of a steel frame, the energy consumption values of ECC-CC and ECC-RAC samples are almost the same; the energy consumption values of samples with UHPC as a wall panel frame are greater, and the gain is greater.

(a) Specimen ECC-CC

(b) Specimen ECC-RAC

(c) Specimen UHPC-CC

(d) Specimen UHPC-RAC

(e) Specimen SF-ECC-CC

(f) Specimen SF-ECC-RAC

(g) Specimen SF-UHPC-CC

(h) Specimen SF-UHPC-RAC

Figure 27 Total energy consumption curve of 8 models

Figure 28 Comparison of total energy consumption

(3) Equivalent viscous damping coefficient

Figure 29 shows equivalent viscous damping coefficients for 8 groups of model wall panel designs. It can be seen from the figure that the equivalent viscous damping coefficient of UHPC-RAC decreases slightly after increasing with increasing displacement, while the equivalent viscous damping of SF-UHPC-CC and SF-UHPC-RAC shows a slight increase first, and then a slight decrease, and then a slow increase as the displacement increases, this indicates that that the addition of a steel frame to the construction of wall panels can alleviate the situation when energy consumption drops too quickly. The figure shows that SF-UHPC-RAC and the sample have the highest energy consumption. This is due to the fact that PCCW-3 initially collects more energy, so it releases more later. PGCM is damaged to a greater extent during the entire loading process, the amount of slippage is large, and the power consumption is the greatest. At an early stage of loading, PCCW-3 and SF-UHPC-RAC have high energy consumption, but with an increase in displacement, the equivalent viscous damping coefficient is similar to UHPC-CC, and the energy consumption is comparable. The large energy consumption in the early stage is mainly due to the higher strength of the filled RAC and the higher stored energy. Energy consumption at a later stage remains the same. This is mainly due to the fact that almost all the fillers of each wall panel were destroyed at this time, and the energy consumption between the destroyed filler and the frame is similar.

(a) Specimen ECC-CC

(b) Specimen ECC-RAC

(c) Specimen UHPC-CC

(d) Specimen UHPC-RAC

(e) Specimen SF-ECC-CC

(f) Specimen SF-ECC-RAC

(g) Specimen SF-UHPC-CC

(h) Specimen SF-UHPC-RAC

Figure 29 Comparison of equivalent coefficients of viscous damping of 8 models

Conclusion

Several conclusions were drawn from this paper based on the power mode and seismic characteristics, and they are listed as follow:

- (1) In the absence of a steel frame from the skeleton curve, it can be seen that the maximum bearing capacity of the four wall panels does not differ much.
- (2) In the presence of a steel frame, the sample with UHPC as the frame of the wall panel has a large bearing capacity; the plasticity of the four wall panels is very good.
- (3) In the absence of a steel frame, the energy consumption values of ECC-CC and ECC-RAC samples are almost the same; the energy consumption value of a sample with UHPC as a wall panel frame is greater, but the increase is not very large.
- (4) In the presence of a steel frame, the energy consumption values of the ECC-CC and ECC-RAC samples are almost the same; the energy consumption value of the sample with UHPC as the wall panel frame is greater, and the magnification is greater.
- (5) The properties of CC and RAC are basically the same and have little effect on the ultimate bearing capacity and plasticity of wall panels.
- (6) Using UHPC as a wall frame can greatly increase the ultimate bearing capacity and energy dissipation capacity of the wall.

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